

Deep Learning enabled Computer Vision in Remanufacturing and Refurbishment applications: Defect Detection and Grading for Smart Phones

Reenu Mohandas, Martin Hayes, Colin Fitzpatrick, Mark Southern

University of Limerick

Abstract

This project combines the use of Deep Learning using Computer Vision for Remanufacturing End of Life consumer electronics products, like smart phones, wearables like fitness trackers and smart watches which could be used in a secondary market alongside new ones to meet consumer demand. The process of refurbishment of these devices is a growing industry but heavily dependent on manual labour which brings in subjectivity of decisions, especially in grading. Deep Learning based computer vision in this work achieves high accuracy, greater than 80% in detecting defects on phones and determining phone grades, to ensure high consistent throughput rate in the remanufacturing process, thereby more sustainability.

Keywords: Deep Learning, Defect Detection, Remanufacturing, Refurbishment, Computer Vision,

1 Introduction

Consumer Electronics and IT & telecommunication equipment including mobile phones, iPads and tablets, wearables like activity trackers and smart watches are the few sectors that benefitted from the autonomous mass production in Industry 4.0. On reaching their End-Of-Life (EOL), these products are commonly referred to as E-waste or WEEE (Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment). Shorter Product Life Cycle, fast changing customer attitudes, and ceaseless roll-out of newer versions into the market, all contributed to WEEE becoming the fastest growing stream of waste. In 2017, the United Nations University published a report, The Global E-waste Monitor Report, stating that only 20% of 44.7 million tonnes (Mt) E-waste generated was properly recycled [Islam, M.T. and Huda, N., 2018] in the year 2016.

Figure 1: Smart Phones for Recycling

Refurbishment and remanufacturing are ways to reduce carbon emissions, by restoring EOL products to reusable states without loss in function. To address the conflict of interest between economic goals and ecological ones, manufacturer's profit in remanufacturing sector should also be taken into account[Cheng, P., et al, 2022]. High variability and difference in availability are challenging factors in this sector, where there is a needs to maintain high throughput rate to combat for the lower price of final products to make the process profitable[Schlüter, M et al., 2021]. This is where AI and Human-in-the-Loop concepts could be of assistance, to ensure faster and more accurate processing of objects and accommodate the wide variability of objects presenting for processing.

2 Purpose of Research

Companies rely heavily on manual labor for sorting, inspection, grading and identification of products and this needs experience, but also introduces subjectivity into the process. To maintain consistency in sorting and identification of defects, determined observation is needed for extended periods of time. This subjective nature adds more pressure to the workers as they can directly impact the economic value of the reverse logistics company [Schlüter, M et al., 2021]. The core problem in this scenario is the human-centric nature of sorting, identification, and defect detection. This is particularly important for determining what polishing process should be chosen for the screens. One of the possible ways to help this is to take humans a step further away and introduce automated systems, AI based identification/detection systems and computer vision to detect, identify and evaluate the products and human operator/personnel can assist by a confirmation or dismissal of suggestions generated by the AI. This will lead way to a more automated re-manufacturing/refurbishment setting with Human-in-the-Loop for further training and updating the initial trained model to be more accurate and faster.

3 Methodology

The problem under consideration is cosmetic damage on a glass screen of an electronic equipment, consider smart phone as a subset. Detection and analysis of scratches will help to determine if they could be sent to rework for processes like polishing which could remove the scratches and upgrade the final value of the equipment in the secondary market. Identification of more severe damage leads to efficient use of time in more valuable products sending the damaged ones to disassembly or eventually even to just recycle the product.

In the experiment, 100 images from smart phone samples were collected and annotated for segmentation of scratch defects, single class detection using Mask-RCNN [He, K. et.al 2017] one of the highly accurate instance segmentation models available in TensorFlow. Segmentation is the process of partitioning an image into constituent parts/regions or objects [E Woods et. al, 2008]. Considered as a one-class problem at this stage, every instance of scratch is separately identified and counted to determine the severity of defect/damage. Semantic segmentation is the process of classifying the pixels in the image into one identified category, without differentiating different object instances [He, K. et.al 2017]. Instance segmentation is in itself a very challenging task that there is detection of each object and then segmenting each instance separately.

Transfer Learning is the machine learning technique to address the problem of low number of training data. The deep learning model could be trained on a generic dataset and the final layers could be fine-tuned using the smaller available dataset for the detection/classification task [Tan, C. et. al, 2018]. Segmentation of scratch and detection of scratches are both performed in the input image. Pixel-wise segmentation helps measure the pixel-wise length of the scratch, detection creates bounding boxes to locate the scratches and obtain the x-min, y-min, x-max and y-max coordinates of the scratch.

Figure 2: phone screen scratch images taken using a digital microscope

Experiment setting and Dataset: Annotation of the image data for instance segmentation was carried out using software ‘labelme’. The Mask-RCNN model is trained on GPU GeForce RTX 2080 Ti using TensorFlow 1.13.1 and the detection function is programmed using Python 3.6 and OpenCV 4.4.0. The reason for using instance segmentation is the dynamic nature of variability in the type and location of scratches. Image data is collected using a digital microscope with (1920 x 1080 camera resolution and 2.5 - 68 (Optical) and 69d - 136.5d (Digital) magnification range(Figure 3).

Figure 3: Digital Microscope

4 Results and Discussion

Figure 4: Segmentation results of scratches on the smart phone screen

The model gives promising results with very high accuracy with the limited dataset used for finetuning. The aim of this work is to grade the smart phone screen based on the cosmetic defects. At this stage of the project, the defect under consideration is scratches on the phone screen. Figure 3 shows the detection results with the number of scratches detected. Currently, any phone with less than 10 count of scratches, is considered Grade 1, 11-30 count of scratches is considered Grade 2 and more than 30 count of scratches is Grade 3. The importance of this classification is to determine the amount of time that need to be spent on the phone(device in general) which determines if the value of product could be improved by less expensive rework or indeed to discard as the rework is expensive and which drives the cost for a secondary product.

Detection model	IOU value	Precision	Accuracy
Mask CNN	0.8314	0.8	0.8

Table 1: Evaluation of results

The Accuracy of Mask CNN model is measured using the IOU score value which is the ratio of Intersection over union of the predicted mask to the ground truth mask of the object under consideration. The models shows high precision and Accuracy values where Precision depicts the rate of True positives per total detection and Recall shows the total True positives against all ground truth instances.

7 Conclusions

The currently trained models give high accuracy in detecting and segmenting the scratches on the phone screen and classify the screen using the number of scratches detected. The experiment is currently in progress and will be further developed into a multi-class experiment with consideration of the different types of scratches the phones are presented with. Future work includes strategies to automatically detect and differentiate cracks from scratches on phone screen and further improve automatic grading to refurbished smart phones.

Figure 5: (a) shows a Grade1 phone high value for secondary use (b) Grade2 phone and (c)&, (d) Grade3 phones.

References

- [Islam, M.T. and Huda, N., 2018] Islam, M.T. and Huda, N., 2018. *Reverse logistics and closed-loop supply chain of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE)/E-waste: A comprehensive literature review*. Resources, Conservation and Recycling, 137, pp.48-75..
- [Cheng, P., et al, 2022] Cheng, P., Ji, G., Zhang, G. and Shi, Y., 2022. *A closed-loop supply chain network considering consumer's low carbon preference and carbon tax under the cap-and-trade regulation*. Sustainable Production and Consumption, 29, pp.614-635..
- [Schlüter, M et al., 2021] Schlüter, M., Lickert, H., Schweitzer, K., Bilge, P., Briese, C., Dietrich, F. and Krüger, J., 2021. *AI-enhanced identification, inspection and sorting for reverse logistics in remanufacturing*. Procedia CIRP, 98, pp.300-305.
- [E Woods et al, 2008] E Woods, R. and C Gonzalez, R., 2008. Digital image processing.
- [He, K. et.al 2017] He, K., Gkioxari, G., Dollár, P. and Girshick, R., 2017. *Mask r-cnn*. In Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision (pp. 2961-2969)
- [Tan, C. et. al, 2018] Tan, C., Sun, F., Kong, T., Zhang, W., Yang, C. and Liu, C., 2018. *A survey on deep transfer learning*. In Artificial Neural Networks and Machine Learning—ICANN 2018: 27th International Conference on Artificial Neural Networks, Rhodes, Greece, October 4-7, 2018, Proceedings, Part III 27 (pp. 270-279).